

OPTIMIZED CARBON NANOFIBRES FOR COMPOSITES TOUGHENING

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SUMMARY

Carbon nanofibres with diameters 150-450 nm were fabricated from polyacrylonitrile via electrospinning and heat treatments. Specially designed MEMS tools were employed to determine the mechanical strength of the polymer precursors and the individual carbon nanofibres. The resulting nanofibres had a small distribution of flaws and the tensile strength of vapour grown carbon nanofibres.

Keywords: PAN, carbonization, nanofibres, nanocomposites

INTRODUCTION

The method of electrospinning allows to mass-fabricate a variety of polymeric nanofibres with controlled diameter and alignment [1-3]. Polyacrylonitrile (PAN) is a commonly electrospun material [4], which can be further used as a precursor to synthesize carbon nanofibres. Such precursor fibres are continuous, well-aligned and dispersed, therefore offering several advantages over conventional vapour grown carbon nanofibres (VGCNFs) when used as toughening agents in polymer matrix composites [5]. The process for making high strength carbon fibres from PAN involves thermal stabilization and carbonization [6]. The former process takes place by heating PAN to 200-300°C in an oxygen containing atmosphere. This oxidation induces cross-linking which results in a stabilized structure that subsequently can be converted into carbon upon treatment at higher temperatures. This carbonization involves heating of the stabilized PAN fibres above 800°C in an inert atmosphere in order to increase their relative carbon content [6].

The mechanical behaviour of individual electrospun PAN-derived carbon nanofibres as a function of heat treatment temperature is largely unknown due to the associated difficulties in experimenting with nanoscale specimens. Zussman et. al. [7] demonstrated in-situ Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM) testing of individual carbon nanofibres and found that their fibres had relatively low Weibull fracture strength of 640 MPa. This value lags significantly when compared to commercial PAN-derived carbon fibres because the process of stabilization and carbonization were not optimized in their work [7]. More recently, a thorough investigation of the mechanical strength of individual VGCNFs by Ozkan et. al. [7,8] showed that the tensile strength of VGCNFs subjected to various treatments is quite smaller than what was assumed before. Hence, it is evident, that experiments with individual carbon nanofibres are required to make

unequivocal conclusions about the effect of processing conditions on the mechanical durability of the resulting fibres.

In the present work, PAN nanofibres were optimized in terms of their fabrication conditions to produce high quality carbon precursors. The selected PAN fibres were processed at two different temperatures to assess the effect of heat treatment on the elastic and failure properties of the carbon nanofibres. These experimental investigations were carried out by Microelectromechanical System (MEMS) based instrumentation [10,11], which overcame major limitations in handling and measuring forces applied to single nanofibres. The results of the present experiments are important in relating the tensile strength and the modulus of carbon nanofibres to their processing parameters so that this category of nanoscale materials can be introduced as effective reinforcement and toughening agents to polymer composites for naval applications.

EXPERIMENTAL METHODS

A homogenous solution of 9 wt% PAN from Sigma-Aldrich with average molecular weight of 150,000 was prepared in N,N-dimethylformamide (DMF). Electrospinning of the PAN solution was carried out with a home-built apparatus at acceleration voltages of 15-25 kV and electrospinning distances of 15-25 cm. PAN nanofibres fabricated at selected conditions were then used as precursors to carbon nanofibres. The PAN nanofibres were heated in air at 5°C/min to 250°C, 275°C and 300°C and for 1 hr. Subsequent differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) studies assisted us in selecting the optimum thermal stabilization parameters. For carbonization, stabilized PAN nanofibres were heated at a rate of 5°C/min to 800°C and 1100°C for 1 hr in a nitrogen atmosphere. The mechanical properties of the PAN nanofibres and the PAN-derived carbon nanofibres were determined by MEMS-based mechanical testing micro-apparatuses that have been developed at our laboratory in the past [10,11]. SEM imaging was employed to evaluate the alignment and the surface morphology of the PAN and the carbon nanofibres as well as to identify critical flaws on the fracture surfaces of tested nanofibres. Finally, the carbon and nitrogen contents of the carbon nanofibres were measured by microcombustion analysis.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The fabrication parameters of electrospinning can be classified as solution parameters (concentration, viscosity, molecular weight and composition), flow parameters (acceleration voltage and acceleration distance) and ambient conditions (temperature and humidity). In the present study, the solution parameters were maintained constant throughout all experiments, whereas the flow parameters were varied to assess their effect on the mechanical behaviour of PAN nanofibres. Figure 1(a) shows an SEM image of relatively aligned PAN nanofibres fabricated at acceleration voltage of 25 kV and acceleration distance of 25 cm. The PAN fibres fabricated at all conditions were equally well aligned and had very uniform cross sections. Figure 1(b) shows the smooth surface of the resulting polymer fibres which is essential for the fabrication of defect free, high strength, nanofibres.

Individual PAN nanofibres with different diameters were tested with the MEMS nanoscale mechanical property measurement method described in references [10,11]. In all cases, the nanofiber strength and the elastic modulus varied monotonically with the its diameter and this trend was more pronounced for nanofibres thinner than 300 nm as shown in figures 2(a,b). To account for variations in the mechanical properties with fibre diameter, the experimental data were divided into three subsets: 200-300 nm, 300-400 nm and 400-900 nm. In the first two diameter subsets, the mechanical properties varied significantly with the fibre diameter, while in the last one the fibre strength and its modulus nearly reached a plateau. Moreover, as shown in figures 2(a,b), the elastic modulus and the strength of 200-300 nm fibres fabricated at 1 kV/cm were significantly larger than those of thicker fibres electrospun at 25 cm. The change in the fibre properties for electrospinning distances 15-20 cm was rather marginal. The origin of this change in the mechanical behaviour were investigated by Fourier Transform Infrared (FTIR) spectroscopy, which revealed that the orientation factor of 200-300 nm fibres fabricated at a spinning distance of 25 cm was larger than 50%, while the orientation factor for fibres fabricated at shorter spinning distances was 21%. Therefore, the higher strength and modulus of the particular PAN nanofibres were, in part, due to higher molecular alignment. This improved molecular alignment for large extensions of the polymer solution is due to the longer travel times of the polymer jet, during which, solvent evaporation occurred while the jet was extended under the electric field. Therefore, the acceleration distance plays a key role in the improvement of the mechanical behaviour of the final electrospun nanofibres.

Figure 1: (a) Aligned electrospun PAN nanofibres, (b) SEM image of an individual PAN nanofiber showing its smooth surface and uniform diameter.

Following the aforementioned mechanical property investigation of PAN nanofibres we selected the acceleration voltage of 25kV and electrospinning distance of 25 cm as the appropriate conditions for the preparation of precursor fibres for carbon nanofibres. Figure 3 shows the DSC results of PAN nanofibres stabilized at three different temperatures. Stabilization of PAN is an exothermic reaction which is completed when the heat flow is reduced to a minimum value. The PAN nanofibres that were stabilized at 250°C produced minimal heat flow and the stabilization reactions were not completed within the 1 hr window of this process. Likewise, during processing at 275°C more heat

flow was achieved in the given time but in the end the reaction was still in progress and it was completed during the given time of 1 hr. Finally, the heat flow plot at 300°C indicates that the exothermic reaction was fully completed within 1 hr as is pointed out by the sharp peak followed by a minimal steady state heat flow. Therefore, all PAN-derived carbon nanofibres in this work were stabilized at 300°C.

Figure 2: (a) Elastic modulus and (b) tensile strength of electrospun PAN nanofibres as function of their diameter and the electrospinning distance for an average electric field of 1 kV/cm.

Figure 3: DSC studies on PAN nanofibres heated at 5 °C/min to 250°C, 275°C and 300°C for 1 hr in air.

Figure 4: Tensile strength experiment showing the MEMS loadcell and the mounted carbon nanofibre.

The stabilized nanofibres were carbonized at 800°C and 1100°C and then tested individually for their tensile strength. Single carbon nanofibres were isolated from bundles similar to that in Figure 1(a). One fibre end was mounted on a miniature loadcell and the other end was attached on a flat surface with a UV-curable adhesive. Figure 4 is an optical image taken during an experiment with a nanofiber. The opening of the double column structure that serves as loadcell was calculated from optical

images recorded at 500x by Digital Image Correlation (DIC) as described in references [10,11]. The loadcells used in this work had a linear response to the applied force until large deflections and were calibrated according the procedure described in reference [12].

Fifteen experiments were conducted with nanofibres carbonized at 800°C and nine with nanofibres carbonized at 1100°C. The experimental strength data were fitted to the Weibull cumulative probability function assuming zero stress threshold:

$$P_f(\sigma_i) = 1 - \exp\left(-\left(\frac{\sigma_i}{\sigma_0}\right)^m\right) \quad (1)$$

where σ_i is the ordered tensile strength which results in the probability of failure $P_f(\sigma_i)$. Linear regression was applied to compute m , which is the Weibull modulus, and σ_0 , which is the characteristic strength. The characteristic strength is defined as the stress at which the probability of failure becomes 63.2% and it represents a measure that is equivalent to the average fiber strength. Figures 5(a,b) show the Weibull probability plots for PAN fibers carbonized at 800°C and 1100°C, respectively.

Figure 5: Weibull probability plot for nanofibres carbonized at (a) 800°C and (b) 1100°C.

The Weibull moduli for both types of carbon nanofibres were about 6 which is an average value for ceramic materials. The larger this value is the smaller the scatter in the flaw sizes that are contained in the nanofibres. This consistency in the Weibull moduli implies that the critical flaw distribution changed very little when higher carbonization temperature was applied. On the other hand, the Weibull characteristic strength increased from ~2.0 GPa for fibres produced at 800°C to ~2.5 GPa for fibres produced at 1100°C. Evidently, the fibre strength is strongly influenced by the carbonization temperature and at 1100°C the resulting fibres had strengths comparable to VGCNFs [8,9].

Figure 6 shows the distribution of tensile strengths as a function of nanofibre diameter for the two carbonization temperatures. Clearly, the tensile strength increases with

decreasing fibre diameter pointing to the possibility for larger flaws residing in larger nanofibres. A fracture surface of a tested carbon nanofibre is shown in figure 7 pointing to such a critical flaw that resulted in purely brittle fracture.

Figure 6: Tensile strength vs. fibre diameter for PAN nanofibres carbonized at 800°C and 1100°C.

Figure 7: Fractured surface of a PAN fibre carbonized at 1100°C. Fracture initiated at the defect pointed by the arrow.

Table 1 summarizes the Weibull moduli and the characteristic strengths of the carbon nanofibres along with C-H-N chemical analysis. The latter actually points out to the complete removal of H and the significant increase in C content when the fibres were heated from 800 °C to 1100 °C, which also explains the increase in the fibre strength. Prior studies on the mechanical properties of PAN-based microscale carbon fibres [13,14] showed that their tensile strength increases for carbonization temperatures up to 1500 °C and then drops due to an increase in the size of C crystallites [13,14]. The elastic modulus, on the other hand, increases monotonically with increasing carbonization temperature due to growth and reorientation of graphitic crystallites along the fiber axis. Such a study is currently under way with the present carbon nanofibres. This work presents a significant improvement over the only previous study [7] because we pursued the optimization of the fabrication conditions for the precursor and the stabilized nanofibres.

Table 1: Weibull modulus, characteristic strength and C-H-N analysis of PAN-derived carbon nanofibres

Carbonization temperature	Weibull modulus	Characteristic strength (GPa)	C-H-N Analysis		
			C (%)	H (%)	N (%)
800 °C	5.9	2.05	81.2	0.37	15.45
1100 °C	5.7	2.5	92.7	0.00	4.06

CONCLUSIONS

It was shown that PAN nanofibres fabricated by electrospinning with acceleration voltage and distance of 25 kV and 25 cm, respectively, represent a very good precursor material for carbon nanofibres with significantly improved tensile strength over previous reports. Stabilization at 300°C and for 1 hr was sufficiently completed before carbonization. The tensile strengths of nanofibres carbonized at 800°C and 1100°C followed Weibull distributions with modulus of about $m=6$, which places the particular fibres among brittle materials with average scatter in their flaw distribution. The results of the present study are significant as they show that aligned and continuous carbon nanofibres with the tensile strength and diameter distribution of commercial VGCNFs can be fabricated as filler material for nanostructured polymer matrix composites.

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